

COLONIAL TRAUMA IN THE POSTCOLONIAL NOVEL AND ITS ARTISTIC EMBODIMENT

Abstract.

There is ample research on postcolonial literature. Thus, the theoretical and aesthetic foundations of this literature have already been established, and certain concepts have been put forward in literary studies. In our article, the works of Arundhati Roy and Monica Ali, the most prominent representatives of postcolonial literature, are examined in the context of colonial trauma and its artistic embodiment, and we conclude that in works of this type, historical events and plots come to the fore in a new way alongside postcolonial reality. History and memory become the basis of the postcolonial novel and reflect the ideological and artistic nature of the work in its search for the national identity of the hero. In many cases, biographical elements present real life to the reader.

Keywords: *postcolonial literature, colonial trauma, artistic embodiment, identical*

The main feature of postcolonial literature is the presentation of the world order in marginal or border conditions. Such literature, as a rule, tells about an individual who has fallen out of society, deprived of his main values - national and cultural identity. At the same time, such heroes, while meeting the requirements of the time, are given the chance to come together with others in the new society. Apparently, for this reason, postcolonial literature becomes an artistic solution to the problem of national and cultural identity and puts forward ways of coexistence of people of different cultures. The interaction and disagreements of the marginalized with the dominant forces of society, the coexistence of different cultures and the struggle for national identity, as a rule, are among the leading themes of postcolonial literature. It should also be noted that postcolonial literature is influenced by the extremely unusual and diverse experiences of immigrants and touches on problems related to multiculturalism, the search for national and cultural identity, the confrontation of immigrants with the natives, and mixed marriages.

Salman Rushdie, Vidiadhar Surajprasad Naipaul, Timothy Moe, Arundhati Roy and Monica Ali, who have made their mark in contemporary British literature, are considered representatives of postcolonial literature. Monica Ali's works "Brick Lane", "Alentejo Blue", "In the Kitchen", "Untold Story", "Love Marriage" talk about ethnic minorities living in England. These families living a migrant life participate in the policy of national-cultural cooperation promoted by the country, and integrate into English society as representatives of a multicultural society. Monica Ali, who was born from a mixed marriage between an English woman and a Bangladeshi young man, notes that the book is not about my family history. It doesn't touch on issues related to my family. But there is something there: it is difficult to determine at first glance, but this is a confession (Ali, 2003).

British writer of Indian origin Salman Rushdie was born in 1947 in Mumbai, India, and later moved to the United Kingdom. His works mainly deal with the colonial and post-colonial period of India, the search for identity, and the clash of cultures. The novel "Midnight's Children" presents the period of Indian independence and the story of a boy born on the same day.

In S. Rushdie's works, he criticizes the history of the British Empire and its constituent countries, such as India and Pakistan. In the novel "Midnight's Children", history and personal memory are presented in an intertwining manner. Rushdie puts forward an interesting idea in the history of postcolonial literature. He presents history from a personal and alternative perspective. This type of narrative is known to be one of the main characteristics of postcolonial literature.

On the other hand, S. Rushdie shows English as an instrument of colonial power, but at the same time puts it forward in the context of new expressive possibilities. In his works, English deviates from the standard norm and is presented in "new" idioms and dialects. Homi Bhabha's concept of "hybridity" is clearly felt in his works. S. Rushdie's heroes are "neither here nor there", in other words, in a state of transition.

S. Rushdie's works deeply explore issues such as the impact on individual and collective identities, the interaction of cultures. S. Rushdie occupies an important place in the history of literature as a postcolonial writer. Apparently, for this reason, his novel "Midnight's Children" is considered one of the most important works written on a postcolonial theme. The work embodies the life of the hero named Saleem Sinai, who was born on the same day as India gained independence and the fate of independent India with him in parallel. In the novel, history is presented not through official documents, but through Saleem's life story. He tells the political events in India as a life story. Rushdie gives different ways of speaking to characters from different social classes, castes and languages. In this sense, in the novel "Midnight's Children" the English language acts as a carrier of the postcolonial position. Rushdie uses the English language to his advantage. This is an artistic solution to the idea of "own voice" in postcolonial literature. As for the characters in Monica Ali's "Brick Lane", they are South Asians from Bangladesh and settled in the Tower Hamlets part of the London borough. Monica Ali is also Bangladeshi, born into a mixed family. She moved to England at a young age and received a higher education. Her character Nazneen also tries to live in a new country tries to live with the English and eventually achieves her desire. Her husband Chanu, on the other hand, can't stand

the existing way of life and leaves England and returns to her homeland. Nazneen's younger sister Hasina, on the other hand, remains in Bangladesh and runs away from home in protest at the unbearable living conditions at a young age. Through Hasina's letters to her sister in London, the fates, outlooks on life, and difficult lives of both women come alive before the reader's eyes throughout the work. Nazneen, who comes from eastern Bangladesh, comes from a poor peasant family. When she was born, the growing unrest in society and the desire for independence divided the territory of Pakistan into two parts, which later paved the way for the creation of the state of Bangladesh. Nazneen's childhood, born against the background of these historical events, is depicted in miserable conditions. After the death of her mother, Nazneen, who lives in a poor cabin with her younger sister, is forced to get married. Her father and relatives send her off to a "decent" husband living in England. The separation of the young girl from her father's house gives her a second life. However, this life brings her new surprises: meeting the bearers of a foreign culture in a foreign country creates new difficulties for her. Her husband, who is older than her, doesn't see Nazneen either, because according to custom, the groom can't see the bride before the wedding. For this reason, he talks to Nazneen's father, comes to an agreement and brings the "bride" to England. The letters of complaint she receives from her sister also make Nazneen unhappy. In every traditional Bangladeshi family, the man is the dominant one and the woman is his slave. Nazneen wants to bring her sister to England. She wants to be as free as the locals, even if she is not as happy as a woman. But she still follows the social customs she adopted in her homeland. Muslim women in Bangladesh live by these rules and abide by them. Mary Whipple writes that "Brick Lane" shows the emotional state of an immigrant who is faced with the possibilities of a new culture that is radically different from the culture of the past" (Whipple, 2004).

Another English writer of Indian origin, Arundhati Roy, was born in the state of Kerala, located on the Malabar coast. She moved to Delhi at a young age and began her creative activity in this city. The writer, who began her literary activity in 1996, became famous after the publication of her first book, "The God of Small Things" (1997), for which she was awarded the Booker Prize (1997). Along with literary creativity, A. Roy, who participated in the socio-political life of the country, became a favorite of the Indian people with her political and journalistic writings. She was awarded the Lannan Literary Awards for Cultural Freedom in 2002 and the Sydney Peace Prize in 2004.

A. Roy's "The God of Small Things" (1997), "The Price of Living" (1999), "The Algebra of Infinite Justice" (2002), "War Talk" (2003), "The Man in the Street's Guide to Imperialism" (2004), "Public Power in the Age of Empire" (2004) tell about the struggle of mankind for survival, existence, memory and identity problems against the background of the desires and aspirations of people born in different families and living in different societies. A number of critics call "The God of Small Things" an autobiographical novel and associate it with the life of the writer. A. Roy, who is the

son of a Syrian Christian mother and an Indian father who is a carrier of Hinduism, treats both religions with great respect and reverence, and also talks about representatives of this religion in the work. According to Alex Tickell, who studied the work in the format of an autobiographical novel, the family values of studying at an architecture school, returning to her grandfather's house with her brother and being the carriers of both religions are also present in the work (Tickell, 2007).

The novel, which has biographical elements, tells about the writer's childhood and her Christian family from the upper class of Kerala. The novel "The God of Small Things" also talks about the caste system, which is important for Indians, the role of women in the family and society, and the life of the Christian population in a society that worships Hinduism. The work, narrated by young twin children, touches on small issues at first glance, but gradually, deep meanings that affect people and change their lives come to the fore against the background of small events. Thus, the small things described in the work create a great meaning and, using the example of a family, sheds light on the discrimination that prevails in society. Interestingly, the writer's metaphor of the God of small things represents the insignificant, silent people in society and their relationships with them. God symbolizes a being who cares for these things and protects them. Atamoglan writes: "In such novels, metaphor becomes the language of aesthetics and socio-cultural reality, serving the reader's communication in the author's story" (Atamoglan, 2020).

It can be seen that A. Roy's novel "The God of Small Things" shows the struggle of small people for survival in the big world in terms of memory and identity problems and conveys certain messages to the reader. A person must remain a person in all circumstances. A person can also take refuge in Small Things in order to live and exist. The essence of a person is great and infinite, this greatness he can preserve in their memory and identity. All Great Things come from Small Things.

Conclusion. As a rule, the hero of postcolonial literature lives in hybrid conditions, in a hybrid reality. Literary criticism calls this reality an "she offers a historic, profound vision" (Gani, 2008). This process leads to unstable conditions, creating gaps in the spiritual world of the individual. The process of identity formation is almost constantly changing and goes through a process of "restoration" and "destruction" that are closely related to each other. The main theme of postcolonial literature is a re-understanding of history, which requires rethinking and sometimes correction. In such novels, historical events and plots come to the fore in a new arrangement related to the postcolonial reality. History and memory become the basis of the postcolonial novel and reflect the ideological and artistic feature of the work in the search for the hero's national identity.

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